

TRANSLATION OF STATIVE VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract – This article gives information about stative verbs and the problems of translating them from English into Uzbek. Problems of stative verbs and their types are discussed. The scientific and theoretical views of several Uzbek and foreign scholars have been analyzed and personal relations have been expressed. Examples from different kinds of works such as S. Maugham’s “Ms. Mabel”, T. Murad’s “Husband and wife”, A. Kahhor’s “Pomegranate” and K. Mansfield’s “Destiny” were compared with the original and analyzed.

Keywords and phrases – equivalence, stative verbs, motion manner, action verbs, lexical-semantic field, methodological inaccuracy, accuracy, adequate, degrees of stative verbs, attraction, lacunae, system asymmetry, autonomy.

In Uzbek, stative verbs can have different expressive semantics. They are positive, negative coloration, gender index, style meaning, attitude semaphore, formal, scientific, artistic, or oral discourse according to the scope of application, and several other indicators. As a result of omitting one or more of these semantics in the translated text, the degree of expressiveness between the original and the translated text is disproportionate. Although such a translation is considered adequate, it cannot be considered equivalent.

Although there are differences of opinion on the two basic requirements for the text of the translation, the concepts of adequacy and equivalence, most research

in translation studies, while interpreting these concepts, stops at the following view: equivalence is a relatively retrospective category and characterized by its nature, it focus on the result of translation. Adequacy is a perspective category, it has a dynamic, translating feature. The basic concept of the science of translation theory and the object of study is equivalence. Equivalence is the equality of the original and the translated text. Adequacy is a term that defines the degree of equivalence of a translated text [Vinogradov V., 1978]. As a result, in translation studies, these two requirements are different from each other. There is also a look that adhesive will determine the level of this equivalent. However, the translation of stative verbs can be harmonized by these two terminologies. For example, the Uzbek language verbs can have one or more meanings in the expression. The appropriate translation of these verbs is called adequate (right) translation and the engine implements meant by translation are called equivalent (complete) translation. The choice of meanings as broadly as possible means that the text is expressively proportional to the original.

Furthermore, if in the text of the original the author repeats a verb of a state of mind, the translator, considering it a methodological inaccuracy, begins to eliminate the tautology in his text. The most used words are replaced by a variant that represents the same meaning. In such a case, the expert may fall into the trap he or she has set himself or herself and choose a unit whose meaning of the expression does not match which is the meaning of the name is not appropriate. In addition, such free movement cannot be understandable to the reader and it blocks the author's original narrative style and skill.

According to linguist L. S. Barkhudarov, "Translation is a speech event from one language into another language and at the same time preserving its content. It follows that the meaning of expression changes during the translation process, the content or the information which is contained in the text, remains unchanged" [Barxudarov L., 1975]. the place of the usage of an expression means its linguistic

context. Maintaining general content despite the change in linguistic context is a priority for the translator.

The translation is a complex creative process. Whether artistic, scientific or formal text translation requires high skill from a specialist. In the process of translation, we witness not only the interaction of two languages but also the confrontation of different cultures and mentalities. Consequently, translation is the intersection of the author's and the translator's inner feelings. Therefore, in identifying problems in translation, it is necessary to refer not only to linguistic theory but also to the deductive method, which can be understood directly from the analysis of translated works. Uzbek translation has its deep history and classical school. Of course, translators also make a worthy contribution to the high share of works translated into non-native languages, in particular, Arabic, Persian, and Russian. When we read classical works that have been translated directly or indirectly into Uzbek, it is impossible not to admit that the authors' ability to speak Uzbek was due to the high skill of the translator. However, it must be acknowledged that the Uzbek school of translation is still inexperienced in other spheres such as translating Uzbek works into foreign languages. There is a great need for mature translators who can skillfully translate Uzbek works into English, who make the Uzbek author close to the English reader, and who speak the Uzbek hero in a truly international English language. The presence of methodological, minor, or serious errors in the translated works is mainly because the translators are still inaccurate, rely on biblical language in translation, are popular, ignorant of spoken English, and do not study the sociocultural aspects of English. To improve translations, it is necessary to compare linguistic phenomena between two languages as a field, and then compile thematic textbooks, philological dictionaries, and large encyclopedic dictionaries based on them, which include linguistic parameters of each lexeme, types of meanings, and semantic relations. Otherwise, the following errors will be observed in the works translated from Uzbek into English: ***Beixtiyor o'zining birinchi muhabbatini – sinfdoshi Xolbuvini esladi...***

Qorong'ini quchoqlab, Xolbuvini bag'riga bosganday bo'ldi. Ko'ngliga oqshomdek ma'yuslik cho'kdi (Т.Мурод “Эр-ХОТИН”) || *Involuntarily he remembered his first love — his classmate Kholbuvi ... He felt her in his chest like an embrace in a dark night. Despair as black as night surrounded his soul* (T.Murod “Husband and wife”, trans.:Sh.Sattorov) We observed several shortcomings in the translation of this passage. The translator translated the phrase *beixtiyor esladi* as *involuntarily remembered*. Here the word signifies that the situation has occurred involuntarily, that the style of the situation is unexpected, instantaneous and it is characteristic of formal speech in English. Such words are not used in artistic or oral speech. Instead, it would be possible to preserve the original poetics of the verb *xotirlamoq* with the help of the translating the verb *to recall* into English. The second separated translation unit is fully and correctly translated without any failings. But the expression *oqshom ma'yusligi* at the end of the passage comes to us in the translation of *kechaning zulmati g'am anduhi*. As a result, the state of mild depression begins to be understood in English as deep distress, which in turn means an expressive imbalance between the translated text and the original. In another translation, although the means are perfectly proportional in content and expression, it is expedient to make the separated passages in English brief and concise.

Turobjon qizardi. U bir zamon betob o'rtog'ini yo'qlab eltgan tarvuzini, bemaza chiqqan bo'lsa kerak, sigirning ohurida ko'rib hijolat bo'lgan edi (A.Қаҳҳор “Anor”). *Turobjon got red in the face. He was in a state of confusion. Once he had felt such confusion when he'd brought a watermelon to his friend's house* (A.Kahhor “Pomegranate”, trans. Kh. Allanazarova). The translation of this passage cannot be said to be equivalent and complete translation to the original. First of all, the information about the illness of the hero's friend, and feeding the cow with the watermelon was omitted. Instead, the word *qizarmoq* was translated into a very long sentence, although the word could only be represented by the word *to blush*. The state of mind of embarrassment is also given in the translation by the

verb *to be confused*, which means *hijolat bo'lmoq, chalkashmoq, chalg'imoq*. This choice of words is also not adequate (correct), and the exact alternative of the word *to scruple* in English is fully understood in the verb *hijolat bo'lmoq*. The expressive imbalance between the original and the translated text can also be observed in the following passage: *Turobjon do'ppisini boshidan oldi va qoqmoqchi bo'lganda ko'zi yirtiq yengiga tushdi, yuragi achidi* (A.Каххор “Анор”) – *When he was about to beat the dust out of it he saw his torn elbow, he **felt bad** about it* (A.Kahhor “Pomegranate”, trans. Kh. Allanazarova). The sema of expression, such as *yuragi achishmoq*, is translated in the form of a strong, emotionally colored mental state translated as *o'zini yomon his qilmoq*. However, in English, there is an emotive-colored alternative to the word *achinmoq* is *to rue*, and it means “*yurakdan achinmoq*”, “*siqilmoq*”.

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